

**METHODS THAT DEVELOP IMAGINATION AND MIND IN MOTHER
LANGUAGE LESSONS**

**ONA TILI DARSLARIDA TASAVVUR VA ZEHNINI
RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI METODLAR**

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Annotatsiya

Ona tili darslarida tasavvur va zehni rivojlantiruvchi pedagogik texnologiyalardan 5-7-sinf o'qituvchilari foydalanishini, tafakkur rivoji uchun xizmat qiluvchi innovatsion g'oya va farazlardan kerakli o'rinlarda innovatsion darslarni tashkil etish ko'lamini orttirish va keng ommaga ona tili darslarida (5-7-sinflar misolida) o'quvchilarda tasavvurni shakllantirish va ijodiy tafakkurni o'stirish jarayonida psixologik so'rovnomalarni qo'llash metodlari. Ona tili darslarida gardnerning 9 aql nazariyasidan foydalangan holda dars jarayonlarini olib borish va o'quvchilarda umumiy natijani bilish ona tili darslarini mazmunli va o'quvchiga to'g'ri yetkazish va qiziqтира olish uchun yaratilgan pedagogik texnologiyalarni dars jarayoniga olib kiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagogik texnologiya, psixologik so'rovnoma, Gardner nazariyasi, tasavvur, zehn.

Abstract

5-7th grade teachers use pedagogical technologies that develop imagination and intelligence in native language classes, increase the scope of organizing innovative lessons in the necessary places from innovative ideas and hypotheses that serve for the development of thinking, and increase the scope of organizing innovative lessons for the general public in native language classes (5 -in the case of 7th graders) methods of using psychological questionnaires in the process of forming imagination and developing creative thinking in students. Pedagogical technologies are introduced into the lesson process in order to conduct lesson processes using Gardner's 9 intelligence theory and to know the general result of the students in the mother tongue lessons, to be able to convey the lessons of the mother tongue meaningfully and correctly to the student and to make them interesting.

Key words: pedagogical technology, psychological survey, Gardner's theory, imagination, mind.

INTRODUCTION

In order to develop the student's level of intelligence and imagination, it is necessary to develop them by approaching classes through various methods and methods. Let's talk about how these methods should be brought to class. The educational method is a system-based guide to organize joint activities of the learner and the teacher aimed at a specific goal. Based on this, the following different methods can be used in the lesson. Recommendations regarding the development of students' abilities to improve their imagination and intelligence in their mother tongue classes, the rules for constantly supplementing and updating knowledge based on their needs, and the psychological characteristics of learners have been developed. The issues of systematically and consciously developing the imagination and mind, increasing the effectiveness of the formation of speech

culture and the development of students' thinking have been extensively analyzed. Determining the level of intelligence, determining the methodological basis of increasing imagination, and opening the way to expand the didactic and pedagogical knowledge of guiding students, and developing verbal competence as a product of creative thought, "Imagination Cloud", "Look at the picture, think", " It is proposed to use interactive methods such as "Conquering the Peak", "Scarabey". The analysis of assignments in the 9-11th grade native language textbook, the formation of oral and written speech competences aimed at expressing the main idea during the execution of such assignments is proven on the basis of the applied methodology.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

"Skarabey" technology is easily accepted by students, because it was developed taking into account the thinking, cognitive and thinking characteristics of the activity. It envisages the use of students' experience, makes reflective observations, has opportunities for active creative search and intellectual experimentation. In addition to education, this method allows you to perform a number of tasks of an educational nature:

[1.1]

In this way, assigning the student to write his thoughts on the topic develops logical thinking, intuition, imagination, perception, ideas and other abilities in students. It is appropriate to include this method in the introductory part of the 5th-7th grade mother tongue lessons as a reinforcement of the previous lesson.

"Tarozi" technology can be used at different stages of studying the educational material, as in the case of grades 7-9. But it gives a high efficiency and result at the stage of summarizing the material, because it implies a high level of awareness of the students and free use of the studied material. Especially high school students of grades 9-11 can do it independently.

This technology can be practiced in small groups and among communities. The following are the main concepts: A topic is an assertion that allows for the conflict of different points of view and does not give preference to any of them. The topic should be chosen in such a way that it opens up all aspects of the studied topic, stimulates the students' information search and inquisitiveness activities. Students will be shown a picture of a scale here.

[1.2]

In each part of the scale, students put what they have learned on the subject in one part, and what they don't understand in another part. At the end, the teacher summarizes their thoughts and concludes the lesson.

In addition to education, this method allows you to perform a number of tasks of an educational nature:

- formation of leadership qualities;
- striving to improve one's personality;
- forming an active outlook on life;
- respect and tolerate different opinions;
- ability to work in a team;
- being able to come to a compromise decision;
- politeness;
- responsibility and interest in the results of their activities.

"Imagination Cloud"

[1.3]

This technology is suitable for students of all grades. Pupils write their thoughts about the topic in their imagination in order to strengthen their knowledge on the subject. The teacher collects the clouds of the students for a quick task in the

group and sticks them to the sky, that is, to the classroom board. And for our harvest to be good, the rain of knowledge will begin to fall. So, dear students, you have learned a lot from today's rain, - said the teacher.

In the "Look at the picture, think" method, students are given pictures related to the previous topic or a new topic. In this case, the students respond to the pictures with resourcefulness and immediacy, based on their imagination. This technology can also be taught to 5-7 graders in the way of working with pictures. Students will be presented with a picture. What do the readers see first of all when they look at this picture? The teacher answers this, then consolidates the student's opinion and summarizes the information by connecting it to a new topic. For example,

You present pictures related to a similar topic to the reader, and they ask what is embodied in these pictures for the first time. Then the opinions of the students are summarized and the teacher draws a conclusion without denying their opinion. Connects to a new topic or reinforces a previous topic. Ana thinks independently, and such thinking is an exercise in imagination. Imagination is the product of this result. Pure imagination has gravity, this is where imagination becomes reality.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Our experimental work shows that the free and independent thinking of students for the development of imagination and intelligence in native language classes is our field of scientific creativity. Therefore, the application of these innovations in practice is an important pedagogical issue. Cultivation of imagination and mental

abilities served to increase the student's speech competence, increase his intelligence and interest. Intellectual and imaginative thinking leads to independent activity, it creates an opportunity to independently understand and put professional sciences into practice, to develop thinking and speech. The realization of these scientific ideas depends on the knowledge and skills of the native language teacher. Our experiences are gratifying in terms of delivering to students and achieving good results with full alignment with the national curriculum, PISA and DTS.

During the experiment, students' interest in the science of their native language, responsibility for the lesson, a number of spiritual and moral qualities, the quality of the lessons and the interactive method and pedagogical technologies showed that the speech competence, imagination, intellect, and thinking of the teacher were developed. In addition, it showed high results in further development of feelings of mutual respect, love for motherland, mother, teacher, and solidarity.

One of the important factors was the improvement of creative activity for independent thinking of students, formation as a person and independent search of the student. To develop the student's intelligence, organizing a lesson using Gardned's 8 intelligence theory gave good results.

Initial distribution indicators of students in experimental areas

2021-2023 academic year

3.1- table

District/City	School	Class	1st quarter	2nd quarter	3rd quarter	4th quarter	Yearly
Andijan city	School 43		70	71	70	71	71
		Control class	69	70	72	74	74

Andijan city	"English life" private school	Experience class	73	74	74	73	74
		Control class	72	75	76	77	77
Jalakuduk district	14th school	Experience class	69	69	70	70	70
		Control class	69	71	72	73	74
Jalakuduk district	62-DIUM	Experience class	71	72	72	74	74
District/City		Control class	72	74	75	76	76

Relevant results at the end of the experiment:

Indicators at the end of the experiment

Table 3.2

District/City	School	Class	1st quarter	2nd quarter	3rd quarter	4th quarter	Yearly
Andijan city	School 43		72	73	75	76	78
		Control class	69	73	75	77	80

Andijan city	"English life" private school	Experience class	73	76	78	80	78
		Control class	72	77	79	81	82
Jalakuduk district	14th school	Experience class	69	69	70	70	72
		Control class	69	74	77	79	83
Jalakuduk district	62-DIUM	Experience class	71	72	72	74	74
District/City		Control class	72	76	78	80	83

The advantages of the lessons conducted on the basis of the pedagogical technologies developed as a result of experiment and testing can be noted as follows:

The student's speech culture, bold and logically correct expression of his thoughts, and the skills of proving them are developed.

The development of imagination and intelligence in 5th-6th-7th grade students makes it possible to increase the competence of personal standards, national universal values.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it is worth noting that meaningful lessons can be organized in each class for the development of students' intelligence. The teacher should organize lesson processes using the above methods and methods. By developing

their imagination during the school period, we will raise a generation rich in inventions in the future. Factors of developing imagination and intelligence are reflected in mother tongue lessons through technological games and lesson development. We can see the scientific basis of this in the following places. "Imagination cloud", "Look at the picture, think?" we can clearly see in the basis of methodical games. Through these game methods, the possibilities of the student's imagination are determined and the examples that serve to enrich it are clarified. Through these, we can find out what great ideas are hidden in the mind of each student, or what new things need to be developed. We can use the lesson to increase the level of knowledge of students and bring scientific news, and invite the student to do the same. The questions and tasks presented in our lesson plan are the scientific aspects of the topic. In addition, asking about the past topic and learning about a new topic will serve for the scientific nature of the lesson. Instructive stories and the question asked at the end of the lesson also serve for educational value. The methodological importance of the lesson is to educate the young generation in the spirit of the mother tongue. Interactive methods and methods serve for students' thinking, imagination and intelligence. Therefore, the above lesson should serve to educate the young generation in a new pedagogical, scientific, educational and modern spirit, in the course of innovation in the field of science. An interactive method can also be inferred based on these SmartArt shapes.

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